

SOCIAL FACTORS AND MACRO SKILLS PROFICIENCY OF TENTH-GRADE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the influence of the social factors on the learning of the four macro skills in English of the tenth-grade students. This research employed the descriptive-correlation and descriptive-comparative designs. The two hundred twenty-two tenth-grade students attending mainstream classes were the respondents. A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used in gathering data. In addition, this study used Mean and Standard Deviation, Independent Samples t-test, One-Way ANOVA, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Results revealed that the influence of social factors among students in learning the four macro skills was moderate. Among the macro skills, speaking skill registered as very satisfactory; writing skill labelled as satisfactory; listening skill described as fairly satisfactory; and reading skill as did not meet expectations. On the comparison of social factors when analyzed according to sex, teacher and peer were found significant; however, on the economic status, no variable was significant. The test of correlation between social factors and macro skills proficiency indicated that self was significantly related to reading and speaking skills. Regression analysis found self as a significant predictor in learning the four macro skills.

Keywords: *Education, English language, Social factors, macro skills proficiency, tenth grade students, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

For anyone who wishes to get an access up the ladder of success, one must consider the development, acquisition of skills and competencies on the fundamentals of the English language; the four macro skills, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing. The development of these four macro skills is the main goal of most if not all English language curricula in the basic education anywhere in the world especially in the non-English speaking countries. It can be observed that English in the past curriculum had been offered from grades one to six. In fact, the medium of instruction in grade three until the present time is English. Yet, despite the promotion of the development of the four macro skills, it has remained a reality that many students lack the skills in reading with comprehension and in speaking, in listening and in writing.

Curricular programs are modified to suit the needs of the students especially in the English subject (DepEd Order: No. 88, s. 2010). The modification made would likely provide training which would boost the listening, speaking, reading, writing, and thinking skills of the students. Moreover, the acquisition of the interactive English learning competencies would be heightened.

This same reality is observed in many schools in which the development of the four macro skills becomes almost the emphasis in all the English subjects. Despite the effort of the schools many students lack understanding, speaking skills, attentive listening, especially the writing skill using the target language.

In United States, individuals living there can read, write, speak, and understand English. But there are also many individuals whose first language is not English. The 2000 census shows that 26 million individuals speak Spanish and almost 7 million individuals speak an Asian or Pacific Island language... (Manual, 2010). With the trend of exodus, diaspora and immigration occurring in progressive countries like in America and Europe, employers require applicants to take tests such as Test of English Language as Foreign Language (TOEFL) and International English Language Testing System (IELTS); exams that focus on the four macro skills of English that are prerequisites before they can qualify for employment. Due to the recent recession happening in America for the past couple of years, United States and other English-speaking countries have heightened their job hiring by virtue of these tests to ensure that open slots will not be put to waste by hiring workers who are inefficient when it comes to listening, reading, speaking and writing (U.S. Department of Transportation, 2010).

In Jordan, Malkawi (2010) has explored some of the factors that have influenced tenth grade students' competence in English listening. He found that approximately 50% of respondents do not want to learn English because it is difficult. Using learning aids such as radio could assist students in improving their listening skills. However, the results of his study highlighted the fact that students use these aids few times. In addition, the teacher himself/herself teaches English without the use of any listening educational aids such as radio or TV and their use of recorder is very limited. Some of the obstacles that

face the respondents in the questionnaire in developing listening comprehension skills include speed speech, limited knowledge of vocabulary, and limited knowledge of the subject in question. English listening comprehension is a complex process that needs gradual development. Improving students' ability as English speakers is a demanding process and there are still many factors, like social factors, influencing language acquisition that need to be considered and further explored.

Also, Tuan (2021) conducted a study for both Vietnamese teachers and students and found that when the students learn speaking, they encountered many problems. According to the teachers, the most common speaking problem was that the students spoke very little or nothing in speaking classes. The students reported that they spoke very little or nothing at all in speaking class. Most of the time, they could not think of anything to say so they used Vietnamese. A significant number of students also claimed that they were fearful of criticism or losing face. They were not motivated to use English to express themselves.

Further, Subbiah and Singh (2015) conducted a study about problems in reading comprehension in English among secondary students in the district of Segamat, Malaysia. They found out that students lack appropriate reading strategies in English. Most students merely read without understanding and do not apply any strategies. In fact, reading in English is an unnecessary 'burden' done only to carry out the tasks during the English lesson. The results of the study show that only three strategies are used quite extensively by the students. These are personalizing, learning with others and understanding and using of emotions strategies. The students did not apply the strategies of predicting, discussing, reflecting, and comparing, which could help them to improve in their performances (Subbiah and Singh, 2015).

Moreover, Huy's (2015) research among high school students showed that many students are not aware of the importance of studying writing skill. They even spent a little investment in this skill. This leads to the low quality of studying writing skill in many high schools. The results of the research reveal that many students made a lot of mistakes in writing English, especially in using preposition and verb tenses.

Likewise, in Thailand, English is considered a foreign language and is used for the purposes of academic advancement, career advancement, and travelling abroad. To cope with the growing local and international demand, several efforts from all parties involved have been made to the Thai educational system to help boost Thai learners' English performance. However, the survey conducted in 2013 by EF Education First, a global leader in international education, showed that Thailand ranks low in English language proficiency in Asia. All over Asia, Thailand's ranking is only above Kazakhstan. Leading the regional league is Malaysia with a score of 58.99, followed by Singapore. The others - India, Hong Kong, South Korea, Indonesia, Japan, Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Taiwan and China - are all over 50 points, while Thailand gained only 44.44 (Sofiana et al., 2013).

On the other hand, Philippines has been among the top contenders in the arena of English-speaking countries. Nonetheless, recent language test results released by the IDP Education Pty. Ltd. Philippines in 2011, an accredited group that administers the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) to Filipinos seeking to work and migrate abroad, showed that the Philippines is no longer the top English-speaking country in Asia. With an overall score of 6.71, Malaysia is now the No. 1 in English proficiency in Asia. The Philippines placed only second with 6.69, followed by Indonesia (5.99), India (5.79) and Thailand (5.71). This was gleaned from IELTS results in 2008, during which some 35,000 Filipinos—70 percent of them nursing graduates applying for jobs abroad—took the language exam to evaluate their English proficiency in reading, writing, speaking and listening (BusinessWorld, Vol. XXI, No. 84).

Correspondingly, in 2006, the series of SWS surveys made among fourth year high school students in Luzon shows that the decline in various aspects of English proficiency happened recently. Proficiency appears to have been stable over 1993-2000 and declined only in 2000-2006.

Looking at rates of change by area, the Balance of Luzon and NCR experienced the steepest declines. Among NCR high school students, 75% in 2000 said that they could speak in English, compared to only 49% this year. The difference is even larger among students residing in Luzon where it was 63% in 2000 and only 28% in 2006.

Another survey by SWS on Personal usage of the English language slightly declined in March 2006 from September 2000 among high school students in Visayas region. In March 2006, only 5% of high school students say they make full use of the English language.

In Mindanao, SWS survey showed that 73% of the high school students read English, 59% write English, 20% understand spoken English, 25% speak English, and 10% think in English. Only 7% claimed they had no ability in the language. The researchers found that many students struggle with a lack of confidence in speaking English. Deficient soft skills among students were highlighted by the teachers interviewed.

Accordingly, in this age of technology, we have seen how communication has been speeded up, ironically it has a negative effect on the learning of the English language. In fact, it has further contributed to the decline in the quality of spoken and written English in the Philippines (Genyo E-learning, 2010). Trends such as chatting, texting and even the “Jejemon” fever have infiltrated the Filipino community; trends that promote the butchering of the English language’s structure, syntax and pronunciation. Even the government has filed the Executive Order 210 which speaks of "Establishing the Policy to Strengthen English as a Second Language in the Educational System" simply because there are still a number, even in college, who are not well-versed in the said language.

Recently, students’ cliques pave way to group linggos or language codes that they make up to establish their order. Example of such is the Jejemon Fever which distorts the English language, as stated above, also proliferating strongly in Davao. Clustering can

also lead to hampering the proper use of English language, for some groups proclaim English speakers as “sosyal” or “hilas.” So, to stay appreciated, some risk their potential to speak the language well.

Additionally, Santos et al. (2022) believes that parents have a lot more to say in the deterioration of the Filipino students’ four macro skills. She said that although children spend more time in school than at home, in this family-oriented archipelago, parents’ praxis and interests, without a doubt, influence their children’s outlook in life. She further states that if the parents don’t speak English well or don’t read references that uphold such an ambiguous language, chances are, their children will also adapt the same practices.

Looking within the metro, Davao City is one of several areas outside Manila where call center companies have been venturing, drawn by lower labor costs and large numbers of high school graduates as available workers. But there has been [a] concern lately that the industry’s growth may be limited by the deterioration of its main advantage: the English proficiency of the work force (Dreisbach, 2024). According to a study conducted by the European Chamber of Commerce of the Philippines, 75 percent of the more than 400,000 Filipino students that graduate from high school and college each year have substandard English skills (New York Times, 2006).

One process, however, that has not been explored in second language research is that of the influence people have upon grade ten students’ learning of the four macro skills. It is true that several significant studies have recently been done on how second language learners develop their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills through different pedagogical strategies employed by the teacher inside the classroom, but the question of how parents, teachers, peers, and self influence the way students learn the four macro skills has rarely been considered. Conducting this research may perhaps give light in determining the factors that may have contributed to the deterioration of English learning among students.

This study, which aimed to determine the extent of influence of social factors on the learning of the four macro skills, was conducted for the following reasons. First, the study may provide an essential analysis of relevant data that could be used by educational institutions, and policy makers, most particularly, the administration in the education sectors as to how to bridge an effective curriculum that supports the need for the English macro skills to be developed among students. The results may help the stakeholders determine the possible actions that they would undertake, whether encouraging those less influential social factors to help in honing the Macro Skills of the students or heightening the ones that are most influential. Second, the study can put forward the most influential social factor that influences the outlook of the tenth-grade students to learn English. Third, this study may also benefit the plight of the parents to help monitor and encourage their children to study the English subject, even at home. Furthermore, students may also benefit from this study a sense of awareness as to which social factor affect them much, and how they may address such social factors for them to develop the skills needed in their academic and non-academic endeavors. Hence, this study was

conducted to shed light on how the social factors influence tenth grade students to study English.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the influence of the social factors on the learning of the four macro skills in the English subject of the tenth-grade students from national secondary schools within the division of Davao City.

Particularly, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of influence of the social factors among grade 10 students in national secondary schools in learning the four macro skills in English in terms of the:
 - 1.1 self?
 - 1.2 parents?
 - 1.3 teacher?
 - 1.4 peer?
2. What is the level of macro skills proficiency of the grade 10 students in national secondary schools in terms of:
 - 2.1 listening?
 - 2.2 speaking?
 - 2.3 reading?
 - 2.4 writing?
3. Is there a significant difference between the social factors and the level of macro skills proficiency of the grade 10 students when analyzed according to:
 - 3.1 sex?
 - 3.2 economic status?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the social factors and grade 10 students' level of macro skills proficiency?
5. Which social factor has a significant influence against learning of the four macro skills?

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1976) which states that an individual learns best in the social environment, which is the primary source of learning, wherein he can specifically imitate a certain model for his current behavior. As such, Bandura's theory supports the social factors (Parents, Teachers and Peers) that the researcher has presented in this study which all play crucial roles in the development of the four macro skills in learning the English language.

Also, Aikens (2008) theorizes that parents are their children's first teachers — exploring nature, reading together, cooking together, and counting together. When a child begins formal school, the parents' job is to show him how school can extend the learning they began together at home. In this study the parents are a factor who may provide or

encourage their children to listen to music, watch television programs, and provide situations where the English language is the medium of communication.

Furthermore, according to Everson's theory (2009), peers include classmates, schoolmates and neighbors. In school for instance, intelligent, hard-working students can affect their peers through knowledge spillovers and through their influence on academic and disciplinary standards in the classroom. Alternatively, misbehaving students may disrupt the classroom, thereby sapping their teacher's time and energy. The diversity of students, classroom environment, student's family income, the number of children with disabilities and racial and gender balance can also create peer influence. Students with learning disabilities may draw disproportionately on their teacher's time; racial or gender tension in the classroom may interfere with learning.

Peer influence may even operate through the ways in which teachers or administrators react to students. For instance, if teachers believe that less should be expected of minority children, they might lower their academic standards when confronted with a classroom that has a high share of indigent students. The other students in such a classroom would experience negative peer effects, not due to the minority students' influence but because of the teacher's assumptions. In this study, peers mean anyone with whom the student associates which in one way or another influences his/her learning of the four macro skills.

Besides, Marley and Szabo (2010) conceive that self is another factor that influences students' learning. Students who are literate in their native language have many skills to draw on when they learn academic English, even when the writing system is different. It is more difficult to teach a concept if it does not exist in the student's native language. Once students grasp the underlying literacy skills of one language, they can use these same skills to learn another language. In this study, self refers to the respondents who may or may not be interested in developing their skills representing the four. This is in line with Lev Vygotsky's concept of Scaffolding (2018), which states that for an individual to attain his full potential as a learner, he must be given the right amount of assistance by a more knowledgeable source.

Too, Barkhuizen (2004) posits that the self influences individuals in learning a language. The self motivates one to study a language in three ways: the view one has of one's self as a language learner, the value one places upon one's self as a language learner, and the ideals one desires as a language learner. Baumeister (1999) as cited by recent study imparts the following self concept definition: "the individual's belief about himself or herself, including the person's attributes and who and what the self is". Besides, the self influences performance in numerous tasks aside from language learning activities as cited by recent study (Coopersmith, 1967).

Further, La Guardia's (2011) Self-Determination Theory is a psychological theory which suggests that intrinsic motivation and internalization, and ultimately identity development, are molded by three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The theory explains that autonomy refers to actions that a learner

initiates and regulates himself. Autonomous actions are willingly engaged in, whereas participating in non-autonomous behaviors make the learner feel compelled or controlled. Competence refers to a learner's feelings of content mastery or intellectual challenge, and is expressed in curiosity, exploration of new or difficult material, etc. Relatedness is the need to feel acceptance by and importance to others (e.g. teachers, parents, peers). The theory suggests that people are likely to devote their energies to language learning activities that promote these three psychological needs; in other words, they are likely to be motivated to learn a language by people, situations, and undertakings that support those needs.

Additionally, Gibbons (2003) affirms that it is fundamental for teachers to take the time to build a learning environment for which students take ownership. And contrary to many stereotypes about disadvantaged students, every student, no matter their background, wants learner autonomy. Hence, self-directed learning bolsters second language learning.

These social factors not only influence the students' language learning behaviors but also affect the four macro skills proficiency of the students. Hadley's (2000) theory on macro skills proficiency presents the notion that the ability of students to communicate in a functional and accurate way using target language is influenced by the social environment where students' dwell. A high degree of macro skills proficiency resulting from a rich social language learning milieu implies having the ability to apply linguistic knowledge to new contexts and situations in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. In addition, students need much encouragement and plenty of learning opportunities to develop their language proficiency. The social environment can be used to promote the development of macro skills proficiency. What is important is the parents', teachers', and peers' commitment to developing students' macro skills proficiency in a systematic and consistent way (Stein, 2011).

Also, listening according to Everson (2009) is a vital skill of language in the sense that it enables someone to understand what other people are saying or communicating. For one to be a good speaker, one must be a good listener. This means that the listening skill enables one to develop certain abilities that will allow a person to be an active listener of information or language coming from the sender. Listening is vital as it leads to effective speaking, which also leads to active reading to know more about a particular subject, and this allows one to write effectively.

Likewise, the ability to participate as a speaker and listener is essential to a student's linguistic, social, emotional and cognitive development at home and in school. Vygotsky (2018) suggests that speaking plays an important part in laying the foundations for a person's intellectual ability in later life. The practice of speaking enables a child to become an active learner and to be able to explore his/her experiences and relationships. Speaking is also a means by which learning across the curriculum can be developed into understanding. The teacher's role in finding ways of planning for and valuing the speaking skill is essential if children are to grow confidently as learners and thinkers.

Another equally important skill is reading. Reading is another skill of language that is vital to enhance communication and language among groups of people. Reading is necessary in the sense that the skill is the same whether in native languages or English. There are several reading skills that are commonly used in language. It can be defined as the process of looking at or understanding the meaning of a book by interpreting the characters or symbols of which it is composed. Cobb (2007) states that the skill of reading enables individuals to develop ways of seeing through written texts, investigate the descriptions of cultures and worlds, and see how the text try to position or influence the reader to be part of the cultures and worlds.

Consequently, according to Zhang (2009), a person is better motivated to study a language when there is an integrated approach towards learning, where speaking is added to reading and writing lessons to ensure that students receive essential practice in oral communication. Since the listening skill is already a natural complement to any true speaking activity, adding speaking opportunities to a reading or writing lesson automatically allows students to integrate at least three skills.

Subsequently, writing is a social activity involving either an implicit or explicit dialogue between writer(s) and reader(s). Writing is further shaped by the community of the writer. For example, written discourse differs considerably amongst a community of friends sharing ideas via email and texts written by biologists (Nystrand, 2006). To illustrate, students' concepts about writing are shaped, at least in part, by institutional decisions about pedagogy and curriculum.

Consequently, success in the classroom and in life depends on the ability to read, communicate, and write (Troutner, 2009). It is true that learners should develop efficient writing ability to express oneself effectively in a written and academic discourse. The people should guide learners around them, especially the teachers, who are responsible for the enhancement of their writing skills.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study consists of three components: independent variables, dependent variables, and moderating variables. The independent variables refer to the social factors which are: parents, teachers, peers, and self; the dependent variables refer to the proficiency in the four macro skills which are listening, reading, speaking, and writing; and the moderating variables are sex and economic status.

The social environment bears a vital role in the learning experience of an individual. Since students are immersed in an environment where positive and negative influences are present and inevitable, their performance in school tasks is most likely affected. The different social factors should be considered if they are to hone the skills of the students, in this case, in the English subject. In schools, the students themselves, their teachers, peers and parents are the social factors that influence such.

The different social factors may either greatly hinder or encourage the development of the students' listening, the significant ability to accurately receive and interpret messages in the communication process, speaking, an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing and receiving and processing information, reading, the process of constructing meaning from written texts, and writing, the activity or skill of marking coherent words on paper and composing text, in learning the English language (Brown, 1994; Burns & Joyce, 1997). If the effects of these factors provide a positive result, most likely the performance of the students in the English subject is promising. As a result, it should be encouraged to further improve the performance of the students. However, if they provide otherwise, the students' performance is at risk. Hence, it should be eliminated or improved so that there would be a greater chance of students achieving a desirable performance.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework showing the relationship of the variables of the study.

Thereafter, the four macro skills proficiency in communication is the most important aspect in learning the English language. Each of them is indispensable in the learning process and teaching performance on behalf of the learners and mentors. These skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing are used as the main vehicle to obtain communicative competence (Everson, 2009).

Baker (2000) affirms that parents contribute to the development or deterioration of students' language skills. She said that parents who are not native speakers of the English language tend to provide little or no opportunity for English language exposure to their children. Parents ensure that their child has a firm grounding in their own language. Parent's language practice influences their children's motivation to learn a second language. If the parents don't use English in casual conversations or read reference materials in English, children's second language learning will only be limited to classroom instruction.

And, Argyle (2016) believes that self influences a language learner based on one's personality, traits, abilities and preferences. This means that the way self influences an individual to learn a language can be shaped and can be altered and can also be affected by other social factors. In this sense, self influence is a product of socialization and development. A person may or may not want to learn a language based upon his perception of himself from what other people think of him as a language learner.

Besides, Du (2013) asserts that self influence motivates students to study a language. Student's satisfaction in learning a language encourages positive outlook in learning. A student who feels a sense of accomplishment in studying a language will be better able to direct his own studies and learning outcomes. Research consistently indicates that the self factor affects students in learning a language more than social elements within the community.

Also, teachers are the providers of materials and situations where the integration of the four macro skills is ensured. Teachers use various instruction techniques to understand and use these learning bridges combining popular culture, images, music, literature and dance between the various language groups represented in the classroom. In this study, teachers as a social factor are the initiators and facilitators of lessons and activities that develop students' four macro skills. This is posited by Everson (2009) who states that teachers were trained to make contextual links from literature to society. Stories, for instance, with a moral or lesson provide a background for an expanded discussion about the students' own feelings about the topics presented in literature. A teacher uses a variety of basic methods to teach vocabulary words, sentence construction and reading fluency. The main goal is to develop a love for reading for the students.

Boonkit (2010) affirms that teachers also focus on language and speech. The class instruction features lessons teaching basic verbal fluency and development of the student's vocabulary for different types of typical conversations. Performance skits, recorded videos and audiotapes take up a large part of the daily lessons. Schools with funds for technology also provide access to videotaping and language laboratories to help

students expand their aural-language skills. Some teachers also use memorized dialog and scripted conversations from texts to expand student conversational skills

Teachers as well integrate speaking, reading and writing, but focus on hours of writing practice each week. Depending on the grade level, students practice basic letter identification and sentence construction. Even high school students must begin with basic vocabulary, but the instruction methods elevate the content to an adult level. Vocabulary at the elementary level, for instance, focuses on a trip to the school cafeteria, while high school or college students might visit a shopping mall for vocabulary. Schools with high-tech language laboratories integrate computerized tablets into the writing instruction methods.

Effective instruction methods lead to the understanding of the four macro skills. The understanding of the strong relationships among the four skills, and the common sub skills that underlie them enables the improvement of the language skills. For example, vocabulary figures prominently in speaking and in writing, and one also needs to understand the meaning of words to read and to write. Other skills such as word choice and awareness of the recipient may be similar for speaking and writing, and awareness of the style used by a message sender is important for both listening and reading (Everson, 2009).

One of the four macro skills proficiency, writing proficiency, is perhaps the most complex of the communication skills and takes the most time to master. As with any other skill, it is improved through practice and a willingness to improve on past attempts. Moving beyond the basics, there are many types of writing and many levels. Writing can be a basic means of conveying information—such as in newspapers—or it can be a tool to create elaborate new worlds, much like those found in fiction novels such as *The Lord of the Rings* trilogy.

In addition, the development of the four macro skills proficiency varies among male and female students. Yang (2002) states that both sexes differ in language proficiency since both process their feeling and experiences differently. The aim of this study is to determine the degree of impact of the social factors to male and female tenth grade students in terms of developing the four macro skills in studying the English language.

And, Chen (2005) upholds that teachers have greater influence to female students compared to male students in terms of studying the English language. Since teachers motivate female students more than male, female learners engage more skills and elements of language than males, who tend to stick with only a handful of language skills. However, Butler (2014) sustains that parental involvement has a meaningful impact on diverse students' success in school when parents get involved in their children's education through open communication with teachers. Parents provide vital insight into a child's learning style and discover how home and social environments can contribute to reading comprehension and language development.

Besides, teacher and parental influence among male and female language learners, economic status of learners may also have an impact on the learning of the four macro skills. The economic status of students is often measured as a combination of income and occupation of the student's parents and/or guardian. It is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group. When viewed through a social class lens, privilege, power, and control are emphasized. Economic status is relevant to all realms of behavioral and social science, including research, practice, education and advocacy. Research indicates that children from different economic statuses develop academic and language skills at the same pace when given ample and enriching learning opportunities (Morgan et al., 2009). Initial academic skills are correlated with the home environment, where low literacy environments and chronic stress negatively affect a child's preacademic skills.

Likewise, the school systems in low economic status communities are often under resourced, negatively affecting students' academic progress (Aikens & Barbarin, 2008). On the other hand, Utley et al. (2011) affirms that students from varying economic backgrounds who are exposed to rich learning environments with regular opportunities perform at the same level of language skills proficiency. Research clearly demonstrates the importance of students feeling valued and respected despite their economic status. A significant part of valuing students and facilitating their success lies in knowing them. Knowing students and the challenges they are facing while studying improves retention rates and the overall success of students.

Moving on to one of the four macro skills, listening is one of the most essential skills that students need to develop due to its crucial part in effective communication. Researchers say that listening has always been considered a crucial component in the acquisition of knowledge and skills from educational institutions (Shiple, 2010). Furthermore, if students are not well-trained to listen for important points in a lesson, they would have great difficulty in grasping the information presented to them verbally. As a result, it is crucial that people within the environs of the students should stimulate them to pay attention and listen well to the teacher. In addition, the students would greatly improve their language competence if their listening skills were finely honed to facilitate their own learning (Yarcia, 2006).

Since listening is a vital skill leading to the development of the other skills, teachers need to prepare appropriate lessons to develop the language proficiency of the students. It should be noted that teachers should help students develop certain skills that would aid them in "understanding and remembering information from lectures" that the learners are undertaking (Huang, 2006). Since listening has been regarded as the most frequently used language skill in the classroom, it should be continuously developed to further enhance the speaking ability of the learners. It is critical that comprehension strategies be examined scientifically to identify effective strategies that could be used by the learners (Marley & Szabo).

One of the popular perspectives which has its bearing up to the present, comes in the form of the learners' peers. Henry Stack Sullivan's (1953) statement which says that

the influence of the family plateaus and the importance of peers increases [come Adolescence]. The demands and opinions of friends can overwhelm the needs of family and, at times, can overwhelm the individuals themselves. Peers interfere with the students' learning of the four macro skills.

Given that listening is an important skill, speaking also needs to be developed among students for effective communication. Teachers', parents', and students' awareness of the speaking ability of their students is necessary to make plans on how they could improve their existing capability. Speaking is one of the four macro skills to be developed as a means of effective communication in both first and second language learning contexts.

In the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) pedagogy environment, how to increase speaking competence and confidence for students tends to be a crucial question among instructors and parents (Boonkit, 2008). Harris (2006) suggests that the complex web of social relationships students' experience—with teachers and peers—exerts the same level of influence on their language learning behavior of the students.

Overall, language learning occurs best when parents, teachers, and peers provide students with frequent opportunities to participate and interact with using English. Constant social communication activity using the target language is the most effective method as it allows students to practice using old and new content vocabulary within a social and learning community. Hence, the four social factors should help one another to build an environment that could boost the language achievement of the students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed the quantitative design utilizing the descriptive-comparative and descriptive-correlation approaches. Descriptive design was used to gather quantifiable information which can be used for statistical inference of the target respondents through data analysis. Its function is to observe, describe, and document the target respondents providing a knowledge base which can act as a springboard for the quantitative nature of this study (Creswell, 2009). In this study, grade ten students served as the target respondents. Comparative design was used to test the comparison between two or more variables. Its function is to explicate the invariance of the subjects while avoiding generating changes upon these subjects (Stangor, 2011). In this study, the comparison between social factors and the level of macro skills proficiency of grade ten students when analysed by sex and economic status were investigated. Additionally, correlation was also used to test the relationship between two or more variables. Its function is to determine whether an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in the other variable (Stangor, 2011). In this study, the relationship between the social factors and grade ten students' level of macro skills

proficiency were also examined. Moreover, the most significant influential social factor was also explored.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in three schools from different districts within the city of Davao. School A is located at Pioneer Village, Buhangin, Davao City. Next, School B is located at Sasa, Davao City. Also, School C is located at Callawa, Buhangin, Davao City. These learner-centered educational institutions are known to produce high school graduates adhering to the Filipino heritage, culture and values with a friendly yet globally competitive demeanour, and whose mission is to develop life skills embedded with values anchored on the K to 12 Enhanced Basic Curriculum of the Department of Education, which also evidently puts into consideration graduates who are fluent in English.

Research Respondents

The respondents were grade 10 students from the national secondary schools. A total of 222 respondents have participated in the research which was selected using purposive sampling technique. The sampling technique aimed to achieve a homogeneous sample whose units share the same characteristics or traits. To attain homogeneity, the selection was based on the criteria that they should be grade 10 students attending regular classes and must not belong to grade 10 students under the Drop Out Reduction Program (DORP) and Alternative Learning System (ALS) since these students undergo a different specialized program established by the Department of Education. The unit of analysis generated 95% confidence interval with 5% margin of error.

Research Instrument

A two-part researcher-made survey questionnaire on sex, economic status, and macro skills proficiency test was used to gather data from the respondents. Part I was made up of 27 items intended to gather socio-demographic information from grade ten students. There was one item for sex, six items for economic status and 20 items for the level of influence of the different social factors using the Likert's tool format. Then, Part II contained 20 items aimed to collect data about the student's macro skills proficiency based on Grade 10 learning competencies in English of the K to 12 Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum as mandated by the Department of Education. Moreover, there were four skills assessed for proficiency test. There were five items for each skill like listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

To ensure that the questionnaire was aligned to the local context, the tool was subjected for content validity by three experts in the field of English language studies. Also, the researcher-made instrument was pilot tested with purposively selected public secondary grade 10 students who did not compose the respondents of the study. This was done to ensure that the errors in the data from the actual respondents of the study, due to the construct of the questionnaire and other factors, shall be minimized.

Afterwards, the results of the pilot testing were recorded for internal consistency and reliability analysis by a competent statistician. Cronbach's alpha was run on a sample size of 30 grade 10 students from a national secondary school. The reliability scores revealed acceptable internal consistency of items for each sub-scale which are as follows: Self ($\alpha=.76$), Parents ($\alpha=.76$), Teacher ($\alpha=0.78$), and Peers ($\alpha=.71$). The overall reliability score of the Part I is ($\alpha=.75$). And, the macro skills proficiency test consists of four subtests in the areas of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The measurement was in the form of multiple choice and performance. The reliability scores revealed acceptable internal consistency of items for each sub-scale which are as follows: Listening ($\alpha=.78$), Speaking ($\alpha=.76$), Reading ($\alpha=.71$), and Writing ($\alpha=.72$). The overall reliability score of the Part II is ($\alpha=.82$). The overall reliability score of the researcher-made instrument in its entirety is ($\alpha=.79$).

The scores of the social factors were interpreted using the range of means from 1.00-1.49 (Very Low), 1.50-2.49 (Low), 2.50-3.49 (Moderate), 3.50-4.49 (High), 4.50-5.00 (Very High). Each of the levels was provided with descriptive interpretation for easy understanding of its meaning.

Mean Interval	Description	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Very High	The situation is always evident
3.50 - 4.49	High	The situation is oftentimes evident
2.50 - 3.49	Moderate	The situation is sometimes evident
1.50 - 2.49	Low	The situation is seldom evident
1.00 - 1.49	Very Low	The situation is never evident

The macro skills proficiency test scores of the students were computed, transmuted and interpreted using the DepEd Order 8, s. 2015 with range of means from Below 75 (Did Not Meet Expectations), 75 – 79 (Fairly Satisfactory), 80 – 84 (Satisfactory), 85 – 89 (Very Satisfactory), 90 – 100 (Outstanding).

Grading Scale	Description	Interpretation
90 - 100	Outstanding	Performance represented an extraordinary level of achievement
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Performance exceeded expectations
80 – 84	Satisfactory	Performance met the all competencies
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Performance met most critical competencies
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Performance failed to meet expectations

The macro skills proficiency test scores for each skill were interpreted using the scales that follow:

A. Listening

Grading Scale	Description	Interpretation
90 - 100	Outstanding	Performance represented intellectual curiosity, attention to details, and sensitivity to ideas, tone and purpose of the text.
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Performance represented purposeful and confident reception of ideas.
80 – 84	Satisfactory	Performance represented willing reception of ideas.
75 - 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Performance represented a lack of skill to receive and process ideas clearly and easily.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Performance represented a failure to receive and/or process ideas listened to.

B. Speaking

Grading Scale	Description	Interpretation
90 - 100	Outstanding	Performance represented phonetically correct and almost error-free oral performance.
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Performance represented comprehensible, with occasional error, oral performance.
80 – 84	Satisfactory	Performance represented frequent errors that confuse listener and require guessing at meaning.
75 - 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Performance represented many errors that interfere with comprehensibility.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Performance represented utterances which are incomprehensible.

C. Reading

Grading Scale	Description	Interpretation
90 - 100	Outstanding	Performance represented emotional and aesthetic sensitivity to the selection.
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Performance represented creative interpretation of the text.
80 – 84	Satisfactory	Performance represented critical evaluation of quality, value, and accuracy of the text.
75 - 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Performance represented literal understanding of explicit and implicit ideas of the text.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Performance represented a failure to recognize and interpret ideas shown in the text.

D. Writing

Grading Scale	Description	Interpretation
90 - 100	Outstanding	Output represented a text with a compelling topic and used transitions, significant support and a conclusion.
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Output represented a text with an interesting topic and used transitions, sufficient support and a conclusion.
80 – 84	Satisfactory	Output represented a text with a topic to inform with transitions, relevant details and a conclusion.
75 - 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Output represented a text with an unclear topic using a few details and transitions.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Output represented a text with an unidentifiable topic with minimal ideas.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the conduct of the research study, the following sequence of events was strictly followed:

Requesting permission to conduct the study. The researcher first secured a Compliance Certificate for Research Ethics Protocol Review from the University of the Immaculate Conception Research Ethics Review Committee. Next, the researcher requested permission from the Graduate School of the University of the Immaculate Conception through the office of the Dean, Dr. Sylvia J. Pidor. After permission was granted by the said office, the researcher wrote letters requesting formal permission to conduct the study in national secondary schools within the division of Davao City. These letters were addressed, in chronological order, to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, school administrators of national secondary schools. After request had been granted to the researcher, he then wrote letters to study coordinators for data gathering purposes.

Administration of the research instrument. The purpose of the study was explained to the respondents. Then, the researcher-made questionnaires were administered by the study coordinators to 222 willing respondents for the study.

Retrieval of the research instrument. After the questionnaires were answered, the study coordinator collected them from the respondents. These answered questionnaires were sent back to the researcher. The data collected were analyzed and interpreted using statistical tools to meet the objectives of the study.

Statistical Tools

Mean was used to determine the level of influence of the social factors among grade ten students in learning the four macro skills in English in terms of self, parents, teacher and peer. Also, this was used to ascertain the level of macro skills proficiency of the grade ten students in terms of listening, speaking, reading and writing. Moreover, t-test and ANOVA were used to assess the difference between the social factors and the level of proficiency of the grade ten students when analyzed according to sex and economic status. In addition, Pearson-r moment correlation was used to measure the relationship between the social factors and grade ten students' level of proficiency. Further, Multiple Regression Analysis was used to determine the social factor which has a significant influence against the learning of the four macro skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Influence of Social Factors Among Grade 10 Students

in Learning the Four Macro Skills in English

Table 1 reveals the influence that social factors have among grade 10 students in learning the four macro skills in English. Four social factors are presented on the table with corresponding mean and standard deviation; these are teacher, parent, peer and self. The overall result indicated a mean rating of 3.424 with standard deviation of .4634 which is described as moderate. This implies that the influence of social factors, like teacher, parent, peer and self, on students' learning of the four macro skills is sometimes evident. In addition, the standard deviation implies that the responses of the respondents in the survey are clustered around the mean indicating homogeneity.

Further, individual result indicated that the teacher factor registered an overall mean rating of 4.025 and standard deviation of .7668 which is labelled as high. This suggests that teachers' influence on students to learn the English language is almost always evident. The result further implies that the teacher almost always requires/encourages students to listen to class discussions done in English with mean rating of 4.275. The teacher also requires/encourages

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
I listen to music in English.	4.266	.8165	High
I watch (and listen to) movies/TV shows in English.	3.788	.8483	High
I speak English during class discussions/activities.	3.068	1.0290	Moderate
I read published materials in English.	2.937	.9299	Moderate
I write notes and letters in English at home and in school.	3.018	1.1214	Moderate
Mean	3.415	.5901	Moderate
My parents like learning the English language.	3.162	1.2587	Moderate
My parents watch (and listen to) news reports, movies, music, and other materials in English, thus, encouraging me to watch (and listen) as well.	3.261	1.1393	Moderate
My parents use English during casual conversations when they talk to me and to others within the family and community.	2.297	1.0342	Low
My parents read newspapers, magazines, books and other texts written in the English.	2.797	1.0968	Moderate
My parents listen and memorize songs in English.	3.505	1.2024	High
Mean	3.005	.7041	Moderate
My teacher requires/encourages me to listen to class discussions done in English.	4.275	1.0073	High

My teacher lets me watch (and listen to) materials (e.g. Movies, TV Shows Music, Audio, Speeches, Literature...) that use English as the medium of communication.	3.973	1.0019	High
My teacher requires/encourages me to speak fluent English during class discussions and casual conversations.	3.995	1.0000	High
My teacher requires/encourages me to read academic and non-academic books/texts and other references materials written in English.	3.968	1.0040	High
My teacher requires/encourages me to practice writing efficient and fluent English observing grammar rules.	3.914	1.2134	High
Mean	4.025	.7668	High
My peers talk to me in English in school and outside the school premises	3.234	1.1049	Moderate
My peers help me understand assignments written in English.	3.329	1.1114	Moderate
My peers prefer to watch English movies and TV series.	3.320	1.0340	Moderate
My peers send texts in English and/or post messages in social networking sites in English.	3.180	.9720	Moderate
My peers read news, novels, magazines and other published materials in English.	3.189	1.0972	Moderate
Mean	3.250	.6028	Moderate
Overall	3.4239	.46343	Moderate

students to speak fluent English during class discussions and casual conversations with a mean rating of 3.995.

Next, the teacher lets students watch and listen to materials (e.g. Movies, TV Shows, Music, Audio, Speeches, Literature...) that use English as the medium of communication obtained mean a rating of 3.973. Moreover, a mean rating of 3.968 shows that teachers require/encourage students to read academic and non-academic books/texts and other references materials written in English. The teacher also requires/encourages students to practice writing efficient and fluent English observing grammar rules with a mean rating of 3.914. These statements suggest that teachers almost always manifest those actions.

Moreover, parent yields an overall descriptive interpretation of moderate with corresponding mean score of 3.005 and standard deviation of .7041. This implies that parents' influence on students to learn the English language is sometimes evident. Meanwhile, on the item, 'my parents listen and memorize songs in English' garners the highest mean rating of 3.505 which indicates that this action is almost always evident by parents in making their children practice the use of the English language.

In addition, In addition, students whose parents like watching (and listening to) news reports, movies, music, and other materials in English, thus, encouraging me to watch (and listen) as well, learning the English language, and reading newspapers, magazines, books and other texts written in the English register a moderate description with mean scores of 3.261, 3.162 and 2.797 and standard deviations of 1.1393, 1.2587

and 1.0968 respectively. These denote that these actions are sometimes evident from parents in propelling students to learn the English language.

However, on the item, 'my parents use English during casual conversations when they talk to me and to others within the family and community', tallies the lowest mean rating of 2.297 with standard deviation of 1.0342. This suggests that parents' use of the English language during casual conversations within the family and community is seldom evident. This further means that the parents of the student respondents use their own language during casual conversations.

In terms of self, it tallies an overall mean rating of 3.415 with standard deviation of .5901 which can be described as moderate. This implies that the students' desire to learn the English language by any means is sometimes evident. Items that demonstrated high description are the following: he/she listens to music in English, and he/she watches and listens to movies/TV shows in English registered mean scores of 4.266 and 3.788. The standard deviations were marked as .8165 and .8483 correspondingly. These suggest that these activities demonstrated by students are almost always evident in learning the English language.

Similarly, items like he/she speaks English during class discussions/activities with mean rating of 3.068 and standard deviation of 1.0290; he/she reads published materials in English with mean rating of 2.937 and standard deviation of .9299; and he/she writes notes and letters in English at home and in school with the mean rating of 3.018 and standard deviation of 1.1214 are labelled as moderate. These indicate that students demonstrating those activities are sometimes evident.

For peer, it garnered an overall mean rating of 3.250 with standard deviation of .6028 which is described as moderate. This implies that peers' impact upon students towards learning the English language is sometimes evident. Further, individual statement indicates that his/her peers talk to him/her in English in school and outside the school premises with mean rating of 3.234; his/her peers help him/her understand assignments written in English with mean rating of 3.329; his/her peers prefer to watch English movies and TV series with mean rating of 3.320; his/her peers send texts in English and/or post messages in social networking sites in English with mean rating of 3.180; and his/her peers read news, novels, magazines and other published materials in English with mean rating of 3.189.

The results suggest that the impact of peer to student or co-peer's desire to learn the English language is sometimes evident. This is backed by the notion of Everson (2009) wherein the interactions among student and peers in the classroom are an essential part of the learning process that influence the lifelong language learning habits of students.

Level of Macro Skills Proficiency of Grade10 students in National Secondary Schools

Table 2 highlights the macro skills proficiency of students. These are listening, reading, speaking and writing. Among the four macro skills, students obtained the highest mean rating of 86 in speaking which can be described as very satisfactory. This implies that students speak words that are comprehensible, are generally correct, though there is a presence of occasional error, occasional hesitation; speakers search for words, can self-correct and can respond to cues.

Next in rank is the writing skill which marks a mean rating of 84 and labelled as satisfactory. This implies that student's written work focuses on a specific topic and follows the rules of paragraph development. Next, the listening skill records a mean rating of 76 which is described as fairly satisfactory. This implies that the students' ability to comprehend text while listening met the most critical listening skill competencies.

Last in rank is reading skill which garnered a rating of 69 which is labelled as did not meet expectations. This implies that students missed the mark in attaining the reading skill competencies, thus, leading to a very poor performance in reading. Further, this indicates for the employment of better techniques or initiatives in addressing the reading difficulties of the students.

Table 2
Macro Skills Proficiency of Students

Macro Skills Proficiency	Mean	Description
Listening	76.00	Fairly Satisfactory
Reading	69.00	Did Not Meet Expectations
Speaking	86.00	Very Satisfactory
Writing	84.00	Satisfactory
Overall	77.00	Fairly Satisfactory

Significant Difference between the Level of Social Factors and Proficiency When Analysed According to Sex and Economic Status

Table 3 displays the comparison of social factors when analysed according to sex. From the social factors listed, two factors are found significant when analysed according to sex. These are teacher and peer factors. Teacher factor generated a t- value of -5.163 with a p -value of .000 which is lesser than .05 in the level of significance which indicates significant. Similarly, peer factor marks a t- value of -3.663 with p- value of .000 which is lesser than .05 in the level of significance which also signifies significant. The results imply that peer and teacher factors significantly differ in treating males and females who are learning the English language. Further, teacher and peer are more accommodating to female than male in teaching the English language. The same result was also found in the study conducted by Chen (2005) wherein academic support from peers and teachers significantly influence English language learning behaviour of female students. Though

teacher support exhibited a significant direct effect on academic achievement for both sexes, the effect was stronger for female students.

On the other hand, self and parent found to be non- significant when analysed according to sex. Self factor records a t – value of -1.933 with a p- value of .055 which is greater than .05 in the level of significance which indicates non- significant. Meanwhile, parent factor registers a t- value of -.282 with p- value of .778 which is greater than .05 in the level of significance which indicates non- significant. The result implies that self and parent factors do not significantly differ in treating male and female students. Equal treatment is given to both male and female by parents and themselves. The above result is in line with the findings of Butler (2014) wherein male and female learners are likely to be particularly susceptible to the influence of parents in learning the English language. Furthermore, as stated by Marley and Szabo (2010), self is a factor that influences students to learn English whether the student is male or female. Thus, parent and self have the same degree of influence to both male and female students studying English.

Also, table 3 shows the comparison of macro skills proficiency when analysed according to sex. Results revealed that speaking skill records a t- value of -2.497 with p- value of .013 which indicates significant. This implies that speaking skill significantly differ with male and female students. Female students demonstrated better speaking skills than male students.

On the contrary, listening, reading and writing skills do not significantly differ with male and female students. The t- values generated are -5.77 for listening, .675 for reading, and -1.465 for the writing skill. Their corresponding p- values are .564 for listening, .500 for reading, and .144 for writing. The result indicates that the p – values obtained are greater than .05 in the level of significance.

This further suggests that reading, writing and listening skills of students do not differ in terms of sex. Performance of both male and female students in the three macro skills is the same. This is supported by the findings of Chen (2005) wherein female learners use more skills than males leading to the holistic development of the four macro skills at nearly an equal rate. Females tend to use speaking skills more often due to socialization while males frequently use the other three skills for independence and self-regulation. This explains better speaking skills of female students. Female students' language learning behavior directly influences their speaking skill.

Moreover, table 3 depicts the comparison of social factors when analyzed by economic status. The overall result of social factors generated an F- value of 1.749 with p-value of .158 which indicates not significant. Hence, it fails to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that social factors do not significantly differ with the economic status of students. Hence, the influence of social factors does not affect students in varying economic status.

Table 3
Comparison of Social Factors and Macro Skills Proficiency When Analyzed According to Sex and Economic Status

Social Factors	Sex	N	Mean	T	P-value	Remarks	Macro Skills Proficiency	T	P-value	Remarks
Self	Male	107	3.336	-1.933	.055	Not Significant	Listening	-.577	.564	Not Significant
	Female	115	3.489							
Parent	Male	107	2.991	-.282	.778	Not Significant	Reading	.675	.500	Not Significant
	Female	115	3.017							
Teacher	Male	107	3.764	-5.163	.000	Significant	Speaking	-2.497	.013	Significant
	Female	115	4.268							
Peer	Male	107	3.101	-3.663	.000	Significant	Writing	-1.465	.144	Not Significant
	Female	115	3.390							

Social Factors	Economic Status	F-value	p-value	Remarks	Macro Proficiency Skills	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Teacher	Less than 7,890	1.693	.17	Not Significant	Listening	2.143	.096	Not Significant
	7,890 to 15,780							
	15,780 to 31,560							
	31,560 to 78,900							
Parent	Less than 7,890	3.778	.011	Significant	Speaking	2.437	.066	Not Significant
	7,890 to 15,780							
	15,780 to 31,560							
	31,560 to 78,900							
Peer	Less than 7,890	.168	.918	Not Significant	Reading	.242	.867	Not Significant
	7,890 to 15,780							
	15,780 to 31,560							
	31,560 to 78,900							
Self	Less than 7,890	5.702	.001	Significant	Writing	2.029	.111	Not Significant
	7,890 to 15,780							
	15,780 to 31,560							
	31,560 to 78,900							
Overall	Less than 7,890	1.749	.158	Not Significant	Overall	.594	.619	Not Significant
	7,890 to 15,780							

Meanwhile, parent and self yield a positive result which tallies F- values of 3.778 and 5.702 with corresponding p- values of .011 and .001 which are lesser than .05 in the level of significance which indicates significant. This implies that self and parent factors significantly differ when analyzed according to economic status. Hence, the higher the influence of the parent and self on the students' performance in the English language, the better is the economic status. This is consistent with the conclusion made by Morgan et al. (2009) wherein students from better economic status tend to have parents who are more encouraging towards studying language skills compared to those who are less fortunate. A family with better economic status is found to have greater impacts on the student's language learning performance. In particular, students coming from families with better economic status are found to perform more superior than their peers from families with low economic status. This is also in line with the findings of Coley et al. (2018) wherein children with better economic status have well to do parents who can provide better learning resources.

Nevertheless, teacher and peer displayed F- values of 1.693 and .918 with p- values of .17 and .918 which are greater than .05 in the level of significance indicating not significant. Thus, it fails to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that teacher and peer factors do not significantly differ when analyzed by economic status. In addition, this means that teacher and peer influence on the performance of students in English seem not to deal with their economic status. This is aligned with the notion of Harris (2006) that teachers and peers exert the same amount of influence to students learning the English language regardless of the student's economic status.

On the comparison of macro skills proficiency when analyzed according to economic status, the overall result indicated an F- value of .594 with p- value of .619 which is greater than .05 in the level of significance which signifies not significant. This implies that macro skills proficiency does not significantly differ with economic status. Further, macro skills proficiency of students is not affected by economic status.

The results indicated that the four macro skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing do not significantly differ in terms of economic status of students by tallying p- values which are greater than .05 in the level of significance. This implies that listening, speaking, reading and writing skills of students are not affected by economic status. This agrees with the findings of Utley (2011) wherein the students' language skills are not affected by their economic status provided that students are given equal opportunities to learn a language as a result of setting suitable learning challenges, responding to students' diverse language learning needs, and overcoming potential barriers to language learning and assessment for individuals and groups of students.

Significant Relationship between Social Factors and Proficiency Level of Grade 10 Students

Table 4 shows the correlation between social factors and macro skills proficiency level of students. It shows that self is correlated with reading and speaking skills. The r- values registered are .172 with p- value of .010 and .234 with p- value of .000. This implies that

there is a significant relationship between self and reading and self and speaking. Hence, as self influence increases in learning the English language, it enhances or increases the reading and speaking skills of students or vice versa. However, self factor is not related to listening and writing. This result corresponds to the findings of Zhang (2009) that integration like reading to speak has many advantages, as it adds variety, encompasses students' different strengths, and creates interactive possibilities by focusing on both productive and receptive skills.

In terms of parent, it shows that it is not related with listening, reading, speaking and writing. The r- values obtained are .051, .101, -.039, and -.091 respectively. The p-values garnered are greater than .05 in the level of significance. This implies that parent is not a significant factor on students' macro skills proficiency. This is in line with the notion of Baker (2000) that parents speak only their mother-tongue to their children, thus, further developing the first language of the child and not affecting the improvement of the macro skills in the second language.

For teacher, it reveals that it is not significantly related with the four macro skills. The r- values obtained are .041, .076, -.019 and .041 respectively. Corresponding p-values obtained are .54, .262, .778 and .545 which are greater than .05 in the level of significance. This implies that the teacher is not a significant factor on the students' macro skills proficiency. This is still in line with the notion of Gibbons (2003) wherein students are within a learning environment that allows for self-directed language-learning process and become less dependent on the classroom teacher, consequently, leading to a more effective enhancement of the four macro skills in English.

The result of peer also indicated that it is not related with the four macro skills. It revealed p – values that are greater than .05 in the level of significance. Hence, peer factor has nothing to do with the four macro skills of students. This is supported by the notions of Sullivan (1953) and the findings of Huy (2015) that peer interaction focuses on conversations using their mother-tongue. Therefore, students are more likely to communicate with peers using their first language not affecting the second language macro skills proficiency of the students.

Table 4
Correlation between Social Factors and Macro Skills Proficiency

		Listening	Reading	Speaking	Writing
Self	Pearson Correlation	.074	.172*	.234**	.070
	p-value	.273	.010	.000	.299
	N	222	222	222	222
	Remarks	Not Significant	Significant	Significant	Not Significant
Parent	Pearson Correlation	.051	.101	-.039	-.091
	p-value	.454	.132	.562	.178

	N	222	222	222	222
	Remarks	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Teacher	Pearson Correlation	.041	.076	-.019	.041
	p-value	.540	.262	.778	.545
	N	222	222	222	222
	Remarks	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Peer	Pearson Correlation	.001	.045	.117	.033
	p-value	.989	.503	.081	.620
	N	222	222	222	222
	Remarks	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant

Regression Analysis on the Influence of Social Factors on the Four Macro Skills

Table 5 displays the significant influence of social factors against learning the four macro skills. The result indicates that self is found to be the significant predictor of learning the four macro skills.

In particular, it shows that the influence of self towards learning the four macro skills has generated p- value which is lesser than .05 and obtained a positive standardized beta of 3.585. This indicates that the regression weight for self in the prediction of macro skills proficiency is significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). Thus, for every unit increase in the level of self, there is a corresponding increase in the macro skills proficiency of students by 3.585. This indicates that self contributes to the learning of four macro skills proficiency of the students.

This result is parallel to the notion of Gibbons (2003) and Vygotsky (2018) wherein a student directs his own language learning and takes the initiative in diagnosing his/her language learning needs, formulating language learning goals, identifying human and material resources for learning, choosing and implementing appropriate learning strategies, and evaluating learning outcomes, consequently, promoting a range of potential objectives for them yielding learner autonomy and successful second language learning through student-centered learning activities.

Table 5
Significant Influence of Social Factors Against Learning the Four Macro Skills

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	p-value	Remarks
	Coefficients		Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	51.358	5.064		10.141	.000	
Self	4.442	1.239	.258	3.585	.000	Significant
Parent	-.803	1.042	-.056	-.770	.442	Not Significant
Teacher	.021	.960	.002	.022	.982	Not Significant
Peer	.349	1.277	.021	.274	.785	Not Significant

Note: R=.255, R-square=.065, F=3.769, p<.05

This is also analogous to the concept of La Guardia (2009) wherein learner autonomy is a basic psychological need and is positively associated with intrinsic motivation influencing one's self to learn a language. The result of this study is also comparable to the assumption of Argyle (2016) and findings of Du (2013) wherein self is a potent influence towards learning a language because this factor could prompt students to improve one's knowledge domain (e.g., understanding of vocabulary and new structure), refine metacognitive skills, and increase motivation in learning a language.

Moreover, the findings are apparent in the results of the regression analysis where 6.05 percent of the variance of macro skills proficiency of students are explained by self as indicated by $R^2 = .605$. This means that 93.95 percent of the variation can be attributed to other factors aside from the single independent variable.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the summary of findings was provided:

1. The overall level of social factors in learning the four macro skills indicated that teacher has the high level of influence followed by parents which yielded a moderate interpretation; Self which tallied a moderate interpretation and peer which garnered a mean rating of 3.250 described as moderate.

2. Among the macro skills, students obtained the highest mean rating of 86 in speaking which can be described as very satisfactory. Next in rank is the writing skill which marks a mean rating of 84 and labelled as satisfactory. Then, listening skill which records a mean rating of 76 which is described as fairly satisfactory. Last in rank is reading skill where it garners the lowest mean rating of 69 which is labelled as did not meet expectations.

3. On the comparison of social factors when analyzed according to sex, results revealed that the teacher and peer generated t-values of -5.163 and -3.663 with p-values of .000 and .000 respectively indicating significance. On the comparison of macro skills proficiency when analyzed according to sex, results indicated that speaking was significant with a t-value of -2.497 and a p-value of .013. On the comparison of social factors when analyzed by economic status, overall result indicated a not significant result with an f-value of 1.749 and a p-value of .158. On the comparison of macro skills proficiency when analyzed according to economic status, result indicated a not significant finding with an f-value of .594 and a p-value of .619.

4. The test of correlation between social factors and macro skills proficiency indicated that self is significantly related to reading and speaking skills with r-values .172 with a p-value of .010 and .234 with a p-value of .000. On the other hand, parent, teacher, and peer indicated that they are not related with listening, reading, speaking and writing skills. The r-values obtained are .051, .101, -.039, and -0.91, .041, .076, -.019 and .041, and .001, .045, .117 and .033 respectively with p-values greater than .05 in the level of significance.

5. The result of regression analysis indicated that self is a significant predictor of learning the four macro skills. It showed the influence of self on learning the four macro skills. This indicated also that the regression weight for self in the prediction of macro skills proficiency was significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). Thus, for every unit increase in the level of self, there is a corresponding increase in the macro skills proficiency of students by 3.585. This indicated that self contributes to the learning of the four macro skills by the students.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Social factors namely teacher, parent, peer and the self influence students to learn the English language were sometimes evident.

2. The level of macro skills proficiency of Grade 10 students in the National Secondary Schools revealed that speaking is labelled as very satisfactory, writing as satisfactory, listening skill as fairly satisfactory and reading skill as did not meet expectations. Speaking skill must be consistently maintained or enhanced while reading skill must be improved through addressing reading difficulties.

3. Teacher and peer were more accommodating to female than male in teaching English language. On the comparison of macro skills proficiency when analyzed according to sex, results indicated that speaking skill was significantly related to sex. Speaking skill significantly differ with male and female students. Self and parent factors significantly differ when analyzed according to economic status. Hence, the higher the influence of the parent and self on the students' performance in the English language, the better is the economic status.

4. There was a significant relationship among self, reading and speaking skills. As self influence increases in learning the English language, there is a greater likelihood or chances that the reading and speaking skills of students will increase or vice versa.

5. Self factor significantly influenced the macro skills proficiency of students. Self factor contributed to the macro skills proficiency of the students.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following were suggested:

1. The level of influence of the social factors may be enhanced by designing team building activities or seminars that may add relevant knowledge to the stakeholders concerned.

2. The reading skill of the students may be improved by conducting remedial reading sessions.

3. Teacher and peer power may be strengthened in dealing with gender issues in learning the English language.

4. Language learning activities may be designed to improve the students' speaking skill. Give them speech enhancement activities by inviting key speakers for the said activity.

5. Self may be capacitated in learning English language by exploring options that are within reach like reading books, writing stories and watching tutorial videos because this might improve reading and speaking skills or the four macro skills proficiency as a whole.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The Deped Ethics Review committee ensured that the study adheres to the Ethics of Research. Next, the researcher made certain that informed consent was properly carried out during the conduct of the study. The researcher explained to the respondents the nature of the study, the reason why they were candidates for the research, the possible risks, benefits, and alternatives associated with the research, and the rights they have as research respondents. Further, they were told that they could withdraw anytime and that they would not be given any reward as respondents. Also, school administrators, together with the other stakeholders, were properly informed about the conduct and significance of the study. Moreover, the results of the study were kept strictly confidential by the researcher and the members of the ethics committee of Deped according to the *Ethics of Research* and as far as permitted by law.

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